

Towards Accurate Bearing Fault Diagnosis in Motors: Identifying the Best Image Conversion Technique

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ABSTRACT

Induction motors are susceptible to various faults, with bearing failures being the most frequent. In this study, a novel approach is proposed for selecting an optimal image conversion technique to improve the performance of bearing fault diagnostics. Time-varying three-phase current signals were collected under different operating conditions of the motor in a controlled laboratory setting. These 1-D current signals were transformed into 2-D images using the Gramian Angular Field (GAF), Markov Transition Field (MTF), and Phase Space Reconstruction (PSR) methods. A variety of image features, including image complexity, structural similarity index (SSI), peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) and edge-based characteristics were extracted to assess the effectiveness of the conversion methods. Among all the methods tested, MTF demonstrated the highest suitability in bearing fault classification based on image processing.

KEYWORDS- *Three-Phase Induction motor, Gramian angular field (GAF), Markov transition field (MTF), phase space reconstruction (PSR), Bearing Fault.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's technological age, induction motors have become a key component in modern industries because of their remarkable combination of beneficial characteristics. However, these motors are prone to several faults, with bearing, stator winding, and rotor issues being the most common. If not addressed promptly, these faults can result in serious problems such as end ring cracks, broken rotor bars, rotor misalignment, uneven air gaps between the rotor and stator, or even complete motor failure (Mishra et al., 2025). Bearings are critical and highly prevalent parts within machines, and their condition plays a major role in determining the machine's overall performance, stability, and longevity (Mishra et al., 2025). Timely detection of bearing faults is essential for the safe and reliable functioning of machinery (Han et al., 2023). Conventional diagnostic methods like vibration, acoustic, and temperature analysis can help identify bearing faults to some degree, but they often require specialized tools, skilled operators, and high-quality data, which can limit their practical application. Over the years, many methods have been proposed for detecting and classifying various motor faults, including bearing failures (Mishra et al., 2025), rotor bar defects (Resendiz-Ochoa E et al., 2021), stator winding faults (Resendiz-Ochoa E et al., 2021), supply voltage unbalance (Resendiz-Ochoa E et al., 2021), and unbalanced load conditions (Resendiz-Ochoa E et al., 2021). Traditional techniques, such as stator current analysis (Liu et al., 2024), vibration analysis (Liu et al., 2024), and acoustic signal processing (Liu et al., 2024), have been widely used, but they often require elaborate setups and specialized knowledge for accurate interpretation. Recent advancements in signal processing techniques, such as frequency domain and time-frequency analysis (Guo et al., 2022), have led to more efficient fault detection approaches. Additionally, machine learning and deep learning algorithms, like support vector machines (SVM), neural networks (NN), and convolutional neural networks (CNN), have shown great promise in automating fault detection and improving diagnostic accuracy (Han et al., 2021). The integration of image-based methods, such as Gramian Angular Field (GAF) (Han et al., 2023, Liu et al., 2024, Han et al., 2021) and Markov Transition Field (MTF) (Han et al., 2021, Liu et al., 2024, Wang et al., 2021, Yan et al., 2022), has become increasingly popular, enabling the transformation of time-series data into image representations that can be processed using computer vision techniques for more effective fault classification. However, despite these advancements, challenges persist, particularly in dealing with complex fault patterns, environmental noise, and real-time monitoring, prompting continued research into hybrid and adaptive solutions for more reliable fault diagnosis systems. Although there have been advancements in fault diagnostic systems utilizing image processing, the author believes that further

research is still necessary to improve their performance. To address this gap, the authors of this paper seek to determine the most effective image conversion technique for diagnosing motor bearing faults. As part of this effort, they conducted a comparative study of three image conversion methods—GAF, MTF, and phase space reconstruction (PSR) (Tang et al., 2024, Dhadphale et al., 2024, Roussel et al., 2023)—with the goal of improving the quality of the generated images, which will serve as features for machine learning or deep learning models in fault classification.

2. SCOPE OF THE WORK

To accomplish the objective outlined above, a customized experimental setup was designed and developed in a controlled laboratory environment. Two operational scenarios were considered for this study: a healthy motor and one with a fault in the inner race of the bearing. Three-phase current signals were recorded under these different conditions. These 1-dimensional (1-D) time series signals were subsequently transformed into 2-D images using three image conversion methods: GAF, MTF, and PSR. Various image features such as image complexity, structural similarity index (SSI), peak signal to noise ratio (PSNR) and edge-based characteristics (Khanzadi et al., 2017, Bharati et al., 2004, He et al., 2022) were extracted from the images produced by each conversion technique. After reviewing the extracted features from all the three methods, it was determined that MTF provided the most effective images for use as features in classification tasks.

2.1. DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF AN EXPERIMENTAL SETUP TO ACQUIRE 3-PHASE CURRENT SIGNALS

In order to examine the types of inner race bearing faults, a series of experiments were conducted using a 2hp, 415V, 3.1A, 3-phase star-connected induction motor. A thin cracked was intentionally induced in the inner race of the bearing to simulate a fault condition. The motor was operated under varying load conditions by mechanically coupling it to a DC generator, which powered a set of lamps. To provide a stable three-phase voltage supply to the motor, three single-phase autotransformers, each capable of adjusting the voltages from 0% to 125%, were installed between the power source and the motor. This setup ensured consistent voltage delivery despite any fluctuations in the supply voltage. Three-phase motor current signals were obtained by interfacing a PC and a YOKOGAWA 3-phase digital power meter with the motor. The motor line currents were recorded at a 20 kHz sampling frequency. The experimental setup is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Picture of experimental set-up

2.2. CASES UNDER STUDY

In the current study, two operating cases of motor i.e., healthy bearing and fault in inner race of the bearing were considered. Experiments were conducted at two different load conditions such as 0% and 25% of full-load to check the effectiveness of the proposed study under variable load conditions. The operating cases under consideration along with their identifiers are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Case studies along with their identifiers.

Sl no.	Case identifiers	Case Description
1	H_NL	Motor with healthy bearing and 0% of full load
2	H_L1	Motor with healthy bearing and 25% of full load
3	IR_NL	Motor with faulty bearing and 0% of full load
4	IR_L1	Motor with faulty bearing and 25% of full load

2.3. USED IMAGE CONVERSION TECHNIQUES

Spectrogram, Recurrence plot, Scalogram (Das et al., 2023, Aimer et al., 2015), GAF, MTF and PSR are some of the techniques for converting time series data into 2-dimensional images. The goal of these image processing algorithms is to encode the temporal information into a spatial structure that merely displays the original signal. Among the aforementioned image conversion techniques, the GAF, MTF and PSR techniques are used in the current scope of study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially, 3-phase current signals were collected from the motor in both healthy and IR fault conditions. Afterward, all the recorded current signals were normalized based on the peak value of their respective phase currents, measured under the healthy no-load condition of the motor. A sample of normalized waveforms of the 3-phase current signals under IR fault conditions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. 3-phase current signals obtained at IR_L1 condition

The phase current time series data were later converted into 2-dimensional images using the three image conversion techniques, namely GAF, MTF, and PSR. The resulting images from the 3-phase current signals under IR fault conditions of the motor, produced using GAF, MTF, and PSR, are shown in Figure 3(a), 3(b) and 3(c), respectively.

Figure 3. (a) GAF, (b) MTF and (c) PSR images obtained from the R-phase current signals at IR_L1 condition

After that, various features such as image complexity, SSI, PSNR, and edge-based characteristics were evaluated from images converted from 3-phase currents using all three conversion techniques. It was noted that the feature values from the R, Y, and B-phase images were very similar across the GAF, MTF, and PSR techniques. Therefore, only the R-phase image features were utilized in the subsequent section to identify the best image conversion technique among GAF, MTF, and PSR. These features are summarized in Table 2. And, the optimal feature values for effective image classification along with the preferred method based on these values have been shown in Table 2. It is important to highlight that images with lower complexity are generally preferred, as simpler images with fewer details are easier to analyse and classify accurately (Liang et al., 2020, Chen et al., 2019). Moreover, images with higher SSI and PSNR values tend to yield better classification results as they ensure higher image quality and clearer feature representation (Jiang et al.,2021). When considering edge-based features, images with high edge density and low boundary length are desirable. High edge density suggests that the image contains complex details characterized by numerous boundaries and transitions, while a low boundary length indicates the presence of clearer and more distinct shapes and edges, facilitating improved classification performance (Zhu et al., 2020).

Table 2. List of features extracted from R-phase GAF, MTF and PSR images.

Methods	Image complexity	SSI	PSNR (in dB)	Edge Based Features	
				Edge-Density	Boundary Length
Preferred value	low	High	high	high	low
GAF	5.69	0.72	15.05	0.02	7242
MTF	2.95	0.99	Inf	0.02	3924
PSR	1.65	0.94	19.45	0.02	12558
Preferred Technique	PSR	MTF	MTF	MTF	

As shown in Table 2, MTF performs better in 3 out of the 4 features. PSR leads in 1 feature only. Thus, MTF can be considered as the most effective image conversion technique out of the three techniques analysed in this study.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive strategy for selecting the most effective image conversion technique for motor bearing fault diagnosis. A thorough evaluation of GAF, MTF, and PSR, followed by an analysis of extracted features like image complexity, SSI, PSNR and edge-based characteristics, revealed that MTF is the most effective method for accurate fault detection. The research highlights the importance of integrating high-quality image conversion techniques with robust feature extraction, enhancing the diagnostic capabilities of motor bearing systems. By combining machine learning, deep learning, and other advanced approaches, the proposed methodology offers a strong foundation for future advancements in industrial bearing fault diagnosis.

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